

SYSTEM FOR COLLECTING AND VISUALIZING INERTIAL DATA FOCUSED ON PARKINSON'S DISEASE

Wanghley S. Martins¹ and Fábio Henrique M. Oliveira²

¹wanghleys@gmail.com, ²fabio.oliveira@ifb.edu.br

^{1,2}Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Brasília - Campus Brasília, Brasília, Brazil

INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a disease of the central nervous system (CNS) that causes the progressive loss of an important neurotransmitter in the human brain, dopamine. In this sense, the progressive loss of dopamine leads to the development of movement-related symptoms in PD patients, such as muscle rigidity, bradykinesia (i.e., muscle slowness), and there is, in more than 75% of reported cases of the disease, tremor in the hand region, as shown in Fig. 1 [1].

Figure 1. Common motor symptoms of PD.

Currently, the diagnosis of PD is made based on the individual's medical history and visual examinations performed by the neurological professional [2].

With that in mind, the main goal of this research is to develop a hardware and software system capable of collecting, storing, processing, and generating a simplified graphical visualization of inertial data to assist health professionals in the diagnosis and prognosis of Parkinson's disease.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order to develop a device capable of collecting inertial data, a wearable hardware for collecting movements of the individual's hand was developed. In the development of the data collection prototype, several types of sensors commonly used in an embedded platform were analyzed. It was found that the use of inertial sensors (e.g., accelerometer) with three axes are sufficient to detect specific movements of the human being [3]. For this, the Arduino prototyping platform was used with the MPU6050 sensor. Also, when performing the first tests, it was necessary to build an end-to-end system¹ to easier control it.

As mentioned, this research focuses on the use of inertial sensors to assist in the computer-aided diagnosis and prognosis of PD. To achieve this, we have employed two triaxial sensors: accelerometer and gyroscope, which allow the visualization of the realized movements. Additionally, by means of feature extraction techniques

the mathematical representation of movements is possible, generating more than ten dimensions of information. In order to facilitate the visualization of the information, this work also focused on the use of a frequently used dimensional reduction technique, the Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The usability of the system was taken into account, a modern and user-friendly interface was developed with QT framework (PySide2) in Python 3.6 language.

RESULTS

The whole system is composed by the hardware (as shown in Fig. 2), which deals with: (i) data collection; (ii) data transmission and software, which includes: (i) connection and hardware control; (ii) data storage; (iii) data processing and (iv) data visualization. Furthermore, the software platform provides, using the feature extraction technique, the classification of individuals with PD (in blue) and without PD (in red), as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 2. Developed hardware prototype.

Figure 3. Clustered subjects - in red subjects without PD and in blue with PD.

CONCLUSIONS

The developed hardware system adequately performs the capture of inertial data of acceleration and spin of the individual and transmits it seamlessly, and wirelessly to the computer. The developed software system is capable of performing the treatment, analysis, and plotting - i.e., the visualization of the intrinsic information from the collected data through the use of feature extraction techniques and dimensional reduction by means of PCA. Together, the graphical interface enables the simplified use of the entire developed system in similar researches and situations. The entire hardware cost about 50 dollars.

REFERENCES

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¹ [Link to the developed system](#)